

Aqueous Solutions of Sodium Aluminate. Part I. Electrical Conductivity.

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No satisfactory proof of the possible number and constitution of sodium aluminates has so far been advanced. Some of these salts have been obtained in a pure state either in the amorphous or crystalline form. The aluminate $\text{Al}(\text{ONa})_3$ was prepared by Thomsen and Sauerwein by heating a mixture of cryolite with calcium carbonate and calcium oxide respectively. Goudriaan (*Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch.*, Amsterdam, 1920, 23, 129; *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1922, 41, 82) succeeded in isolating the aluminates $4 \text{Na}_2\text{O}$, $3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, $16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $4 \text{Na}_2\text{O}$, $3 \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, $10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in diamond-shaped and needle-like crystals respectively. Allen and Rogers (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1900, 24, 304) obtained a hard mass of $\text{Na}_2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_4$, $4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, by repeatedly digesting a solution of aluminium in sodium hydroxide with alcohol.

But the existence of a large number of sodium aluminates, chiefly meta-aluminate, has been inferred from a study of the properties of solutions of aluminium hydroxide in sodium hydroxide. Since one mole of aluminium hydroxide dissolves in one mole of sodium hydroxide, Prescott (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1880, 2, 27) thought meta-aluminate was present in the solution. The cryoscopic data obtained by Noyes and Whitney (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1894, 15, 694) and by Slade (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1911, 17, 26) support the above conclusion.

Wood (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 417) measured the solubility of aluminium hydroxide in sodium hydroxide and found that his results agreed with the above assumption. But Slade (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1912, 18, 1) pointed out that the ratio of Na: Al could be anything from 2:1 to 10:1 depending upon the conditions of precipitation of the aluminium hydroxide.

Hildebrand (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 866) and Blum (*ibid.*, 1913, 35, 1499) measured the changes in the hydrogen-ion concentration, when sodium hydroxide was gradually added to a solution of aluminium chloride. From the breaks in the curve obtained by plotting the volume of NaOH against the hydrogen-ion concentration, they concluded that NaAlO_2 was present in solution.

Lyte (*Chem. News*, 1885, 51, 109) studied the action of aluminium sulphate on dilute and concentrated solutions of sodium aluminate and inferred from the products obtained that the dilute solutions contained $\text{Na}_3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_4$ and the concentrated ones $\text{Na}_6\text{Al}_2\text{O}_6$. Bayer (*Chem. Zeit.*, 1888, 12, 1209) found that when alumina and soda (1:1) were ignited and the product treated with water, pure $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was deposited until the solution contained Al_2O_3 and Na_2O in the ratio of 1 to 6 (moles). But when the ignited mass was placed in as much NaOH solution as was present in the mass, the solution remained clear, thus suggesting that $\text{Na}_4\text{Al}_2\text{O}_5$ and $\text{Na}_{12}\text{Al}_2\text{O}_9$ are really chemical compounds.

Mahin, Ingraham and Stewart (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 30) studied the action of ammonium nitrate on sodium aluminate and found that the ratio of $\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ was always greater than 2:1. By electrolysing a solution of sodium aluminate, they also found that the ratio of aluminium hydroxide precipitated to the amount of oxygen evolved at the anode was greater than 2:1. Hence they concluded "Colloidal properties of aluminium hydroxide play a far more important part in conditioning its solubility in bases and there is room for doubt as to whether aluminates exist as salts at all." The increased quantity of aluminium hydroxide they obtained was explained as due to the coagulation of the colloidal solution. These conclusions were criticised by Blum (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 36, 2388), who showed that there was no room for doubting the existence of the salt NaAlO_2 .

Hantzsch (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1902, 30, 297) measured the electrical conductivity of a solution of sodium aluminate with the progress of time and found that the solution first changed into a hydrosol of aluminium hydroxide, then into a gel and finally gave a crystalline precipitate of aluminium hydroxide. Dhar and Chatterjee (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16, 122, *addenda*; *Chem. News*, 1920, 121, 258) found no change in the electrical conductivity of sodium hydroxide on the addition of

small quantities of aluminium hydroxide and hence concluded these to be cases of peptisation and not of chemical combination. On the other hand, Slade and Polack (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1914, 10, 150) found that although the electrical conductivity of a solution of sodium aluminate showed no change in the first few hours, yet it altered considerably afterwards. They, therefore, concluded that no colloidal alumina was formed and confirmed their conclusions from the ultramicroscopic study of the above solutions.

It appears, therefore, that the exact nature of the solutions of aluminium hydroxide in sodium hydroxide is not correctly known and the results of a systematic study of the various properties of these solutions are wanting. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to measure the electrical conductivity of solutions containing different ratios of Na_2O and Al_2O_3 .

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of solutions.—Solutions containing different ratios of Na_2O and Al_2O_3 were prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity of aluminium hydroxide in 2N solutions of sodium hydroxide.

Sodium hydroxide solution, free from carbonate, was obtained by preparing a concentrated solution of sodium hydroxide (100 g. in 100 c.c. of water) in a Jena-glass flask, keeping it for 48 hours to allow the carbonate to settle and filtering the supernatant liquid through glass-wool. The strength of the solution was determined by titrating it with a standard acid; 2N solution, used in this investigation, was prepared by diluting this whenever required.

Redistilled water, free from carbon dioxide, was used throughout and the stock solutions were kept in a Jena-glass flasks in an atmosphere free from carbon dioxide.

For the preparation of aluminium hydroxide required for a particular ratio, a weighed amount of aluminium chloride was dissolved in distilled water and the hydroxide precipitated by ammonium hydroxide. The precipitate was washed until free from Cl-ions.

The aluminium hydroxide thus prepared was treated with the calculated quantity of sodium hydroxide solution (2N) and the

mixture boiled in a Jena-glass flask till all the aluminium hydroxide was dissolved. The solution was filtered and made up to 250 c.c. In this way the most concentrated solution of any series containing a definite ratio of Na_2O and Al_2O_3 was prepared. The solutions, thus prepared, were allowed to stand for 48 hours before use. The solutions of different strengths were obtained by diluting the stock solution.

The ratio of Na_2O to Al_2O_3 in these solutions was further checked by estimating Na_2O and Al_2O_3 by Lunge's method (*Z. anorg. Chem.* 1890, 227). It was found that solutions containing greater amount of Al_2O_3 than represented by the ratio 1:1 could not be obtained because of the low solubility of aluminium hydroxide in sodium hydroxide.

Burettes, pipettes, measuring flasks, etc. were standardised according to the standard methods.

The electrical conductivity of solutions containing Na_2O and Al_2O_3 in the ratios (i) 1:1, (ii) 2:1, (iii) 3:1, (iv) 4:1, (v) 3:2 (vi) 5:2, was determined at dilutions between 2 N and 0.01 N at 30° by Kohlrausch's method. As the object of this investigation was not extreme accuracy in the absolute values of the conductivities, the slight change in conductivity, brought about by boiling the solution in Jena-glass flask, has not been taken into consideration.

The resistance box and bridge wire were calibrated by the standard methods. The results obtained are given in the following tables, in which the following symbols have been used:

N = concentration of solutions in term of the normality of sodium hydroxide.

Δ = equivalent conductivity in r.o.

Several readings were taken for the resistance of a solution and mean of these readings was taken for calculating the specific conductivity (σ); the equivalent conductivity was calculated from the formula

$$\Delta = \frac{\sigma \times 1000}{N}$$

The equivalent conductivity has been plotted against the concentration and against the ratio of Na_2O and Al_2O_3 and the curves obtained are shown in Figures I and II.

TABLE I.

Ratio $\text{Na}_2\text{O} : \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$	Conc. of NaOH (N).	Equivalent conductivity (Δ) in r.o.					
		1:1	2:1	3:1	4:1	3:2	5:2
	2.00	58.75	97.50	67.70	123.80	73.20	83.00
	1.00	70.65	112.80	82.20	153.80	90.03	101.90
	0.666	76.78	126.10	93.11	167.00	107.80	109.20
	0.500	81.26	130.50	99.24	177.06	117.96	122.20
	0.400	81.00	133.60	103.70	181.60	119.60	129.50
	0.333	—	143.60	117.40	187.90	134.30	135.80
	0.285	102.30	145.20	131.20	188.50	140.30	141.90
	0.250	105.36	143.48	137.60	191.00	141.60	147.28
	0.220	109.40	—	143.80	195.30	—	155.10
	0.200	111.50	154.00	152.00	195.35	149.50	153.50
	0.100	113.00	161.20	185.00	—	157.00	163.80
	0.050	118.90	168.80	203.20	—	166.20	175.90
	0.010	122.00	184.00	222.00	—	181.00	198.00

Discussion.

It will be seen from Table I, that the equivalent conductivity of sodium hydroxide is considerably decreased by the addition of aluminium hydroxide. These observations are not in agreement with those of Dhar and Chatterjee (*loc. cit.*). The results described above agree very nearly with those calculated by extrapolating the conductivity-time curves obtained by Slade and Polack (*loc. cit.*).

FIG. 1.

From Fig. 1, it will be seen that the equivalent conductivity of solutions, containing different ratios of Na_2O and Al_2O_3 , increases with dilution. The increase in the conductivity is much greater in dilute solutions than in the concentrated ones. The solution containing the ratio 3:1 shows very rapid changes below 0.50 N. The increase in the conductivity of these solutions on dilution is due to an increased concentration of mobile hydroxyl ion, probably caused by the greater degree of hydrolysis of the salts present in the solutions.

The value of the equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution of the solutions containing different ratios of Na_2O and Al_2O_3 has been determined by the method adopted by Harman (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1155) for the purpose. The equivalent conductivity is plotted against the logarithm of normality and the following values have been obtained for the equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution by extrapolating the curves shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2.

TABLE II.

Ratio	... 1 : 1	3 : 2	2 : 1	5 : 2	3 : 1	4 : 1
Δ_{∞}	... 123	192	196	220	236	240

FIG. 3.

Very interesting conclusions are obtained from Fig. 3, in which the equivalent conductivity has been plotted against the ratio. In the case of the dilute solutions, it will be seen that

(1) the equivalent conductivity of sodium hydroxide solution to which alumina is added falls rapidly but not linearly until the ratio 2:1 is reached;

(2) the equivalent conductivities corresponding to ratios 2:1 and 3:2 are almost equal, which is rather remarkable;

(3) the equivalent conductivity falls rapidly as the ratio is changed from 3:2 to 1:1.

There are no sharp changes in the curves at low dilutions (below 0.25 N) and hence no inference regarding the existence of any aluminates in solution can be drawn from a study of these curves.

In the case of the concentrated solutions, it is noticed that

(1) the equivalent conductivity of sodium hydroxide solution to which alumina is added falls rather rapidly until the ratio 3:1 is reached;

(2) there is a sharp change in the curve corresponding to the ratio 3:1;

(3) the equivalent conductivity, at and above 0.25 N, increases as the ratio is increased from 3:1 to 5:2 and 2:1 and then falls, as the ratio is changed to 3:2 and 1:1.

The sharp change at the ratio 3:1 would seem to indicate the formation of the salt $\text{Na}_6\text{Al}_2\text{O}_6$ in solution. This salt is probably

hydrolysed to a very small extent in concentrated solutions and hence there is such marked suppression of the mobile hydroxyl ions and the consequent fall in the equivalent conductivity. The degree of hydrolysis of the salt increases in dilute solutions and hence no marked change of direction is noticeable in the upper three curves.

The increase in conductivity of solutions of ratios 5:2 and 2:1 may appear abnormal at first sight. But considering the relative increase in the sodium hydroxide content as the ratio is increased from 1:1 to 3:2 and 2:1, the observed increase in the equivalent conductivity is expected. The formation of the salt $\text{Na}_6\text{Al}_2\text{O}_8$ in solution which, as stated above, probably, hydrolyses to a very small extent in concentrated solutions, produces a considerable fall in the OH-ion concentration, inspite of the increase of sodium hydroxide in solutions of the ratios 5:2 and 3:1 and hence there is a fall in the equivalent conductivity in solutions of these ratios.

As solutions containing aluminium hydroxide, dissolved in sodium hydroxide in ratios greater than 1:1, could not be obtained because of the limited solubility of the former in the latter, no information could be obtained from these experiments regarding the existence of the well known salt $\text{Na}_2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_4$.

The hydrogen-ion concentrations of these solutions are also being measured and in view of these measurements, the points raised here will be further discussed in a subsequent paper.

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